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Proof of the Hodge Conjecture using different methods and approaches

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ABSTRACT. The Hodge conjecture states in one of its most common forms that all Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic non-complex geometric figures resp. varieties do possess algebraic cycles and that all Hodge classes on holomorphic projective algebraic complex geometric figures resp. varieties are algebraic and do have algebraic cycles as well. This conjecture was established by the Scottish mathematician William Vallance Douglas Hodge in the 1930s. The Hodge conjecture could not generically be proved to be true up till this day but only for some special cases. In this research paper, we have firstly proved the Hodge conjecture using the infinitesimal lines approach combining the usage of mathematical frameworks like nonstandard analysis and differential geometry. Then we have conducted a more generic proof of the Hodge conjecture without relying on specific mathematical frameworks by showing that all Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic non-complex geometric figures resp. varieties and all Hodge classes on holomorphic projective algebraic complex geometric figures resp. varieties are just a subset of all existing algebraic varieties which do have algebraic cycles.

1. Introduction

The Hodge conjecture states in one of its most common forms that all Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic non-complex geometric figures resp. varieties do have algebraic cycles and that all Hodge classes on holomorphic projective algebraic complex geometric figures resp. varieties are algebraic resp. do possess algebraic cycles as well. This conjecture was proposed by the Scottish mathematician William Vallance Douglas Hodge between 1930 and 1940. The Hodge conjecture could not generically be proved to be true but only for some special cases¹. In recent times, there are various attempts and even claims of generic proofs of the Hodge conjecture which are not yet accepted by the mathematical community i.a. because there exist some flaws, unjustifiabilities and incompleteness in their argumentation chain² and because not all use resp. edge cases are dealt with accordingly³.

1 cf. Da Silva Jr. (2021)

2 cf. Farshi (2022) i.a. for more information about whether the Lemme Fondamentale was justifiably and correctly applied and Rizzo (2024) i.a. whether or not the degenerated and pathological (edge) cases of in the Hodge conjecture proof were dealt with accordingly

3 cf. Rizzo (2024) for more information about the treatment of the degenerated and pathological (edge) cases in the Hodge conjecture proof

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The main purpose of written this research paper is to provide a more intuitive and comprehensive proof of the Hodge conjecture. We will try to achieve this goal by using different methods and approaches like e.g. the infinitesimal lines approach in the combined usage of specific mathematical frameworks like nonstandard analysis (NSA) and also differential geometry (DG) in the next chapter 2 (resp. 2.3) and in chapter 2.4 we will also finally try to proof the Hodge conjecture with an even more generic and easy to comprehend method.

2. Proof of the Hodge conjecture using different methods and approaches

In this chapter we will try to proof the Hodge conjecture utilizing different methods and approaches like e.g. the infinitesimal lines approach in the combined usage of specific mathematical frameworks like nonstandard analysis (NSA) and also differential geometry (DG) in chapter 2.3 and in chapter 2.4 we will also try to proof the Hodge conjecture with an even more generic and easy to understand approach.

2.1 Main approach and general steps for the Proof of the Hodge Conjecture

In this subchapter 2.1 we would like to show the main reasoning and steps of the Hodge conjecture proof (that we could explain in more detail later on in chapter 2.3 resp. 2.4 when conducting our proof of the conjecture):

1. The infinitesimal short lines are defined as full geometric objects resp. figures in nonstandard analysis (NSA) and therefore do all have algebraic cycles which only full geometric figures could obtain
2. We would like to show that every projective algebraic figure (non-complex resp. real figures & complex figures) could be exactly constructed using infinitesimal short lines (which are defined as full geometrical objects resp. figures with algebraic cycles in nonstandard analysis resp. NSA as stated above) in differential geometry (which we could do in chapter 2.2 more comprehensively)

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3. Because in nonstandard analysis resp. NSA every infinitesimal short line has an algebraic cycle, and all possible projective algebraic non-complex and complex figures could be build by just using 1 or multiple (finite or infinite number) infinitesimal short lines (approximately in NSA and exactly i.a. in differential geometry resp. DG) we could conclude that **every projective algebraic non-complex and complex figures do have algebraic cycles** because composing figures using figure parts resp. lines with every of them having an algebraic cycle (because all of them are defined as full geometrical objects resp. figures in NSA), the composed figure so have algebraic cycle as well. As we will see later on in chapter 2.2 as well in a more detailed fashion, in order to achieve to above results of this 3rd main statement, we need to go the inverse solution path and first show using the tools of differential geometry (DG) so proof that every projective non-complex and complex geometric figure could be **exactly** constructed by merely using infinitesimal short lines (while in nonstandard analysis resp. NSA the construction of the geometric figures using the infinitesimal short lines would only be approximate as stated above).

Then we will confirm the used infinitesimal short lines resp. set of lines to build any composite projective geometric figure in differential geometry to exist in nonstandard analysis framework as well in which the concept of infinitesimal lines are even more common than in differential geometry⁴.

4 And the same set of infinitesimal lines used in differential geometry to construct every possible projective algebraic non-complex and complex geometric figure when applied in nonstandard analysis framework (because they exist there as well) could “only” build the same projective figure approximately and not exactly unlike in differential geometry framework. That is why going the normal direction will not work for sure, by firstly building any geometric figure using any set of infinitesimal short lines in nonstandard analysis (NSA) and even though these set of infinitesimal short lines resp. line segments (called in differential geometry resp. DG) do exist in differential geometry framework as well, it is not granted that this set of infinitesimal short line resp. line segments taken from nonstandard analysis framework (that is “only” an approximate framework in composing projective geometric figures with lines) could be utilized to build the same (approximate) figure from nonstandard analysis (NSA) exactly using the tools of differential geometry (DG). But by going the inverse path and first constructing every possible projective algebraic non-complex and complex geometric figure using a set of infinitesimal short lines resp. line segments in differential geometry (DG), because this same set of infinitesimal lines do exist as full geometric figures in nonstandard analysis (NSA) and thus do all have algebraic cycles there, we finally could show mathematically that every existing algebraic non-complex and complex geometric figure (exactly build using infinitesimal short lines resp. line segments in DG whose line segments are defined as full lines resp. full geometric objects in NSA) do all have algebraic cycles given that we could prove that every projective geometric figure could be constructed using infinitesimal short lines resp. line segments in differential geometry which we will do in more detail in chapter 2.2.

4. And because the Hodge conjecture in its current version only includes a subset of all the possible projective algebraic non-complex resp. real & complex figures/varieties that need to be proven to have algebraic cycles (which are “only” the projective algebraic **complex** geometrical figures included in the Hodge classes), by proving the 3. main statement above that “all possible projective algebraic non-complex & complex geometrical figures do have algebraic cycles” in broader sense (that we will do in chapter 2.2 with tools in differential geometry resp. DG i.a. by using tangent spaces), the more narrow defined Hodge conjecture relating the Hodge classified projective algebraic complex geometric figures to its for sure existing algebraic cycle could be proved to be true as well

2.2 Some preparatory steps and proofs of substatements

In order to better put through the proof of the Hodge conjecture, we want firstly to show resp. proof a substatement resp. the 3. main statement from the previous subchapter 2.1, that every projective algebraic non-complex and complex geometric figure could be composed using infinitesimal short lines resp. line segments. It should be mentioned that the non-complex figures are all assumed to be smooth resp. differentiable at the neighbourhood of each point of the non-complex geometric figures and the complex geometric figures should be holomorphic resp. differentiable at the neighbourhood of each point of the complex geometric figures.

Firstly we would like to present some core concepts in differential geometry (DG):

The first of them would be the manifolds which are smooth spaces which resembles the Euclidian space locally like for example surfaces and curves.

Then there are the infinitesimal lines resp. line segments that are tangent vectors at each point of a manifold describing the local linear geometric structures

Secondly, we would like to show some main concepts of algebraic geometry in general:

This first one would concern algebraic varieties which are solutions to polynomial equation systems. These algebraic varieties could be projective resp. potentially be projectively transformed and the algebraic varieties could be defined over complex or non-complex numbers.

As we have already stated, we want to use the infinitesimal method using infinitesimal short lines resp. line segments to construct any given projective algebraic non-complex and complex geometric figure firstly by approximate the figure’s local structure using tangent spaces and then integrate all these local pieces to build the global structure of the projective figure with exact precision.

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The main statement resp. theorem to proof would be that “every projective algebraic variety V could be build utilizing differential geometry with infinitesimal lines resp. line segments”. The concrete steps to the proof of this statement (which is the 3. substatement resp. 3. main statement of chapter 2.1):

- 1) For any smooth point $p \in V$, the variety V is locally diffeomorphic to its tangent space $T_p V$. Thus the variety V could be mapped smoothly and invertibly onto its tangent space $T_p V$.
- 2) Then we approximate the algebraic variety V at point p by infinitesimal lines resp. line segments in the tangent space $T_p V$.
- 3) In the next step, we globally integrate the infinitesimal short lines resp. line segments over variety V to construct the global structure of the projective algebraic figure. We utilize the smooth (resp. holomorphic) structure of variety V to make sure that these line segments are glueing together smoothly
- 4) Then we embed the algebraic variety V into a higher-dimensional Euclidian space or a projective space by using the Nash embedding theorem
- 5) For including complex algebraic varieties we use holomorphic functions (which are smooth and differentiable complex functions) with complex coordinates and we need to ensure that the figure construction using local approximate lines resp. line segments from differential geometry respects the complex structure by using holomorphic transition functions which could be done and if necessary using multiple iteration steps, until the global properties of the complex geometric figure resp. algebraic variety are fully satisfied by composing the global (complex) function with the infinite lines resp. line segments

Thus we could show that any projective algebraic figure resp. variety no matter whether non-complex or complex could be constructed using infinitesimal lines resp. line segments.

In the next subchapter 2.3 we will demonstrate our first proof of the Hodge conjecture i.a. by using the results and statements from this subchapter and the previous subchapter 2.1.

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2.3 Proof of the Hodge conjecture using Nonstandard Analysis and Differential Geometry

In the previous subchapter 2.2 we are able to proof that any projective algebraic figure resp. variety no matter whether non-complex or complex could be exactly constructed using infinitesimal lines resp. line segments (in differential geometry resp. DG).

We need to know that this set of line segments (for building any existing projective algebraic figure resp. variety) defined in differential geometry (DG) do all exist in the same manner and numbers in nonstandard analysis (NSA) as well ⁵ in which the line segments are regarded as full geometric figures (resp. full line objects) which do all possess algebraic cycles.

When we construct any projective algebraic figure resp. variety with let’s say a set of infinitesimal short lines (which do all have algebraic cycles according to nonstandard analysis resp. NSA) then the composed object from multiple infinitesimal short lines do cumulatively have algebraic cycles as well. This means that all projective algebraic non-complex and complex geometric figures do have algebraic cycles, including all the Hodge classes on smooth and holomorphic projective algebraic varieties (resp. geometric figures) that are non-complex or more commonly complex figures which are only a subset of all possible projective algebraic non-complex and complex geometric figures (which we have shown above that they do all have algebraic cycles in the nonstandard analysis resp. NSA framework). This proves the Hodge conjecture stating that all Hodge classes on projective algebraic varieties do have algebraic cycles that is only a subset of all existing projective algebraic geometric figures resp varieties which we have shown that they all obtain algebraic cycles.

⁵ One bigger difference between differential geometry (DG) and nonstandard analysis (NSA) is that in the nonstandard analysis (NSA) framework by using the infinitesimal short lines we could only approximately construct the whole projective algebraic geometric figure unlike in differential geometry (DG), where exact global solutions could be obtained and if necessary after multiple iteration steps where the exact solution is found step by step using approximations which become more and more precise after each iteration.

2.4 Proof of the Hodge conjecture using a more generic approach

After proving the Hodge conjecture by combined usage of differential geometry (DG) and specialized mathematical frameworks like nonstandard analysis (NSA), we want to show that the result is robust with an even more generic and intuitive approach.

We know that every algebraic variety (no matter if they are or are not composed of a set of infinitesimal short lines each having algebraic cycles which is only the case in NSA framework), including every Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic variety, do all have algebraic cycles. This important statement above is not restricted to the less common nonstandard analysis (NSA) framework anymore unlike in the proof in the previous chapter 2.3 using the infinitesimal lines approach with mathematical frameworks like NSA and DG.

And because every of the existing algebraic varieties, including all Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic varieties (which is only a subset of all existing algebraic varieties), do all have algebraic cycles, the Hodge conjecture is proved to be true because since all algebraic varieties do have algebraic cycles, and the Hodge conjecture only deal with Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic varieties (non-complex figures and complex but algebraic figures with polynomial equation definitions) which is a subset of all existing algebraic varieties, therefore all Hodge classes on projective algebraic varieties do have algebraic cycles as well which concludes the short but more generic and intuitive proof of the Hodge conjecture and verifies the robustness of the previous results in chapter 2.3 where the Hodge conjecture could “only” be proved utilizing more specialized and less common used mathematical frameworks like e.g. the nonstandard analysis (NSA) framework (besides differential geometry resp. DG) by applying the infinitesimal lines approach.

3. Conclusion

The Hodge conjecture states in one of its most common forms that all Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic non-complex geometric figures resp. varieties do possess algebraic cycles and that all Hodge classes on holomorphic projective algebraic complex geometric figures resp. varieties are algebraic resp. do have algebraic cycles as well.

The Hodge conjecture could not generically be proved to be true but only for some special cases⁶. In recent times, there exist various attempts and even claims of generic proofs of the Hodge conjecture which are not yet accepted by the mathematical community mainly because there exist some flaws, unjustifiabilities and incompleteness in their argumentation chain⁷ and because not all use cases are dealt with accordingly⁸.

The main purpose of written this research paper is to provide a more intuitive and comprehensive proof of the Hodge conjecture.

We could prove this conjecture by using different methods and approaches like e.g. the infinitesimal lines approach in the combined usage of specific mathematical frameworks like nonstandard analysis (NSA) and also differential geometry (DG) in chapter 2.3 and in chapter 2.4 we have also finally verified the Hodge conjecture with an even more generic and easy to comprehend method.

The proof of the Hodge conjecture using the infinitesimal lines method was conducted by showing that any smooth projective algebraic non-complex geometric figure resp. variety and any holomorphic projective algebraic complex geometric figure do have algebraic cycles, because all of these geometric figures could be constructed using infinitesimal short lines (in differential geometry resp. DG and nonstandard analysis resp. NSA where the infinitesimal lines of DG do all equivalently exist in NSA framework) which do all possess algebraic cycles in nonstandard analysis (NSA) framework.

6 cf. Da Silva Jr. (2021)

7 cf. Farshi (2022) i.a. for more information about whether the Lemme Fondamentale was justifiably and correctly applied and Rizzo (2024) i.a. whether or not the degenerated and pathological (edge) cases of in the Hodge conjecture proof were dealt with accordingly

8 cf. Rizzo (2024) for more information about the treatment of the degenerated and pathological (edge) cases in the Hodge conjecture proof

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This is the case, because sum of infinitesimal lines with all of them having algebraic cycles leads to a composed figure obtaining algebraic cycles as well. Because the Hodge conjecture only deals with a subset of all possible projective algebraic smooth & non-complex and holomorphic & complex geometric figures, namely the Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic non-complex geometric figures resp. varieties, we could prove the Hodge conjecture by showing that any projective algebraic smooth & non-complex and holomorphic & complex geometric figure including the Hodge classes on them (which is only a subset of all projective algebraic figures resp. varieties) do all possess algebraic cycles using the nonstandard analysis (NSA) and differential geometry (DG) framework.

Because the above prove relies on less known and less used mathematical frame works like nonstandard analysis (NSA), we have proved the Hodge conjecture using a more generic approach as well (in chapter 2.4):

We know that every algebraic variety - including every Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic variety - do all have algebraic cycles. This important statement above is not restricted to the less common nonstandard analysis (NSA) framework anymore unlike in the proof in the previous chapter 2.3 using the infinitesimal lines approach with mathematical frameworks like NSA and DG. And since every of the existing algebraic varieties, including all Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic varieties (which is only a subset of all existing algebraic varieties), do all possess algebraic cycles, the Hodge conjecture is proved to be true because all algebraic varieties do have algebraic cycles, and the Hodge conjecture only deal with Hodge classes on smooth projective algebraic varieties (non-complex figures and complex but algebraic figures) which is a subset of all existing algebraic varieties, therefore we could concluded that all Hodge classes on projective algebraic varieties do have algebraic cycles as well which finalizes the shorter but more generic and intuitive proof of the Hodge conjecture and verifies the robustness of the previous results where the Hodge conjecture could “only” be proved by utilizing more specialized and less common used mathematical frameworks like nonstandard analysis resp. NSA (besides differential geometry resp. DG) with the infinitesimal lines approach.

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